

Simultaneous analysis of four isoflavonoids in *Radix scutellariae* by RP-HPLC with DAD

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Abstract : A simple method was described for the determination of four isoflavonoids in *Radix scutellariae*. The isoflavonoids in the sample were extracted using 70% methanol and analysed by reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) with diode array detector (DAD). Chromatographic separation was performed using a Finnigan Surveyor HPLC system with a Akasil C18 column at 25 °C and gradient elution of two solvents as mobile phase : solvent A, 0.2% glacial acetic acid; solvent B, acetonitrile. The effluent was monitored using a DAD set at 263 nm. The average recoveries were 91.58–108.34% (n = 6) with standard deviation below 3.59%. Limits of detection and quantification were 0.20–0.29 and 0.60–0.87 µg/mL, respectively. The samples were injected directly by a simple and rapid sample pre-treatment. The proposed method was successfully applied to the determination of *Radix scutellariae* samples.

Keywords : HPLC, DAD, *Radix scutellariae*, isoflavonoid.

Introduction

In recent years, numerous studies have focused on the determination of isoflavones in many plants such as red clover, vegetable soybeans, soybean feeds and other plants^{1–4}. Those plants contain a class of phytochemicals known as isoflavones that appear to be able to affect the diseases process of heart and osteoporosis^{5–7}. They have estrogenic activity and have been associated with prevention of breast and prostate cancer as well as cardiovascular disease, particularly in the area of women's health⁸. Genistein and daidzein are the two major isoflavones in soybean, both compounds occur naturally, predominantly in their glucosidic forms⁹. Genistein and daidzein are strong antioxidants and account for 80% of antioxidant potential of soybean^{10–12}. Genistein is also considered a phytoestrogen and acts as an antiestrogen in a similar manner to the anticancer drug Tamoxifen¹³. *Radix scutellariae* (*Scutellaria Baicalensis* Georgi) is traditional chinese medicines used to treat some diseases and contains some isoflavones also found and extensively studied

in soybean, including aglycones and their glycoside and glycoside malonate derivatives¹⁴. In *Radix scutellariae*, the main isoflavones are formononetin and biochanin A, with smaller concentrations of daidzein and genistein¹⁵.

Several methods to characterize the content of isoflavones in medicinal herbs using liquid chromatography with both ultraviolet and/or mass detectors, as well as capillary electrophoresis with electrochemical detection have been reported^{16–19}. Most HPLC methods developed for the quantitation of isoflavones in medicinal herbs have disadvantages like the isolation of analysts or being very time consuming procedures²⁰. However, there was no report on the quantitation of isoflavones in *Radix scutellariae*. The aim of this study was to develop and validate a simple, fast and affordable HPLC method for separation of daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein, whose chemical structures are shown in Fig. 1. The optimized procedure was then applied to the quantification of flavonoids in medicinal herbs *Radix scutellariae* in China with fast sample preparation process.

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein.

Results and discussion

Sample preparation :

Most methods described to analyze the isoflavones of medicinal herbs in the literature have a very complex sample preparation. In order to develop a simpler and faster procedure, several conditions were tested. Different concentration ethanol were tested (data not shown) to ensure a complete extraction of isoflavones from their complex matrices. Best results were achieved using 70% methanol by applying ultrasonic treatment, analyses were made in triplicate. The extraction time was also evaluated, the best extraction rate of isoflavones was obtained when the sample solution was treated with ultrasonic bath for 20 min.

Optimisation of chromatographic conditions :

The separation of isoflavones on RP columns was based on the hydrophobic interactions of individual isoflavones with the stationary phase. The retention times of the separated substances depend on their solubility in water and/or their hydrophobicity, it was demonstrated that retention time increases as the hydrophobicity of the substance on the RP columns increases. The retention times of the separated isoflavones could also be influenced by other factors, like their affinities to the stationary phase, which could be modified by using different functional groups, changing the mobile phase composition and the profile of the gradient elution, modifying the temperature of the column, these principles were proposed by Lee *et al.*²¹. Since the individual isoflavones contain polar groups, ionisation needs to be limited without compromising resolution, to achieve this gradient elution with a mobile phase containing acid is often used in RP-HPLC. In this study, the composition of the mobile phase was optimised by adding glacial acetic acid to the aqueous phase to deter-

mine their effects on the enhancement of resolution, inhibition of adenosine ionisation and elimination of peak tailing of the target compounds. As a result, a mobile phase containing glacial acetic acid was selected together with acetonitrile which gave satisfactory resolution and a stable baseline. To improve separation selectivity and increase efficiency, different percentages of glacial acetic acid were investigated. Because the viscosity of glacial acetic acid was larger, the internal pressure of HPLC system would be increased with the increase of acid concentration. Finally, a mobile phase consisting of acetonitrile and 0.2% glacial acetic acid was chosen for the determination of isoflavones in *Radix scutellariae*. Typical HPLC-UV chromatograms of the mixed standard solutions of daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein and the sample of *Radix scutellariae* at 263 nm are presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The chromatograms of the four isoflavones in the mixed standard solutions and *Radix scutellariae* at 263 nm wavelength scan [daidzin (11.88 min), daidzein (15.07 min), genistin (19.92 min), genistein (33.84 min)].

Method validation :

Appropriate method validation according to well an established protocol is required by regulatory authorities. This procedure is intended to ensure that an analytical method is specific, accurate, precise, linear and robust over a specified range.

LOD and LOQ were calculated using 3 SD/b and 10 SD/b (SD is the standard deviation of the curve and b is

the slope of the curve). A good linear relationship between the corresponding peak areas and the concentrations of the analytes was achieved. The limits of detection for this analytical method as the signal to noise ratio S/N = 3 were determined for daidzin (0.21 µg/mL), daidzein (0.22 µg/mL), genistin (0.20 µg/mL) and genistein (0.29 µg/mL), respectively. The limits of quantification can be considered as three times the limit of detection. The limit of detection of daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein was detected at 254 nm, 263 nm, 282 nm and 288 nm, respectively. LOD and LOQ values are reported in Table 1.

Precision was evaluated by means of repeatability and reproducibility measures. Table 2 shows these data with the validation parameters of RP-HPLC methods. It is evident that the proposed method is more sensitive and precise.

Daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein standard materials were dissolved in the mobile phase yielding the same concentration of 20 µg/mL. Then, 0.5, 1.00, 2.00, 4.00, 8.00 and 10.00 µg/mL of the mixed standard solutions were prepared to yield a series of working solutions for the calibration curves.

Evaluation of each point was repeated three times and each calibration curve was fitted by linear regression. The RSDs of the slope of the four lines were 1.34%, 1.01%, 1.57% and 2.15% for daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein respectively. The linearity between peak area and concentration was analyzed using four calibration curves obtained in three different days with standard solutions of daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein. In this study, the linearity of the HPLC method was investigated for daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein in the range 0.20–225 µg/mL, 0.12–230 µg/mL, 0.42–210 µg/mL and 0.4–160 µg/mL, respectively. The calculated re-

Table 1. Linearity and detection limits for the analytes

Compd.	Regression equation ^a	Correlation coefficient (r ²)	LOD (µg/mL)	LOQ (µg/mL)
Daidzin	Y = 33377.1X + 1670.53	0.9991	0.21	0.63
Daidzein	Y = 51137.4X + 5760.61	0.9995	0.22	0.66
Genistin	Y = 39040.5X + 25.78	0.9994	0.20	0.60
Genistein	Y = 126937X + 2756.56	0.9998	0.29	0.87

^aY = Peak area, X = concentration of compound (µg/mL).

Table 2. Precision values for daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein

Compd.	Daidzin (RSD%)	Daidzein (RSD%)	Genistin (RSD%)	Genistein (RSD%)
Repeatability	1.42	1.24	1.37	2.81
Reproducibility	2.73	2.28	2.34	4.94

Repeatability was obtained from replicates of the complete procedure. This was evaluated by way of six consecutive replicates of the analysis on the same *Radix scutellariae* sample. The repeatability was assessed by calculating RSDs in six measurements. RSDs of daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein of six independently prepared extracts of *Radix scutellariae* were less than 2.81%, indicating that the conditions used in the quantitative analysis were satisfactory.

Reproducibility was obtained as the relative standard deviation of results of six analyses of *Radix scutellariae* over 7 days were less than 4.94%.

gression equation, correlation coefficients (r²) by HPLC-DAD method were showed in Table 1.

In order to determine the accuracy of the method, recovery experiments were performed. Samples of *Radix scutellariae* were spiked with known amounts of daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein standard solutions. The accuracy of method was determined by measuring the reference standard recovery in triplicate at three levels from 80% to 120% of the method concentration (5 µg/mL), added at the beginning of the procedure. The spiked samples were then prepared and analysed by the proposed HPLC-DAD method. The results are shown in Table 3. The average recoveries were 99.83–103.22% (RSDs < 3.21%) for daidzin, 93.54–108.34% for daidzein (RSDs < 1.68%), 91.58–107.65% for genistin (RSDs < 3.59%) and 96.53–104.38% for genistein (RSDs < 3.46%), respectively indicating the suitability of the developed method in quantifying the concentration of isoflavones in *Radix scutellariae*.

Table 3. Results of the accuracy of the method (n = 3)

Compd.	Added (µg/mL)	Detected (µg/mL)	Average recovery (%)	RSD (%)
Daidzin	4	4.13	103.22	1.73
	5	5.28	105.61	3.21
	6	5.99	99.83	2.41
Daidzein	4	3.71	93.54	0.79
	5	4.94	98.76	1.68
	6	6.50	108.34	1.32
Genistin	4	4.31	107.65	3.59
	5	4.62	92.46	2.64
	6	5.49	91.58	2.71
Genistein	4	3.86	96.53	1.92
	5	5.13	102.54	3.46
	6	6.26	104.38	2.83

Analysis of Radix scutellariae :

The validated method was applied for determination of isoflavones in *Radix scutellariae*, six parallel samples were analyzed. The results are shown in Table 4. The highest amount of isoflavones was daidzin, genistein was not detected in *Radix scutellariae* sample.

Table 4. Results of isoflavones in *Radix scutellariae* (n = 6)

Compd.	Daidzin	Daidzein	Genistin	Genistein
Mean result (µg/mL)	10.78	1.76	0.77	nd
RSD (%)	2.61	3.28	2.94	nd
Wt. %	1.08	0.18	0.08	nd

nd : not detected.
Wt. % : g/100 g.

Experimental*Plant materials* :

The samples of *Radix scutellariae* belonging to the family Scutellaria Baicalensis Georgi were purchased from a traditional Chinese medicine store in Xinxiang, China and identified by Li-Juan Yang at School of Pharmacy of Xinxiang Medical University. The *Radix scutellariae*, after being washed with water and dried in the shade for several days, was powdered.

Chemicals and reagents :

Acetonitrile, methanol and glacial acetic acid (HPLC grade) used in the study were purchased from Fisher Scientific (Pittsburgh, PA, USA). Daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein used for establishing calibration curves were

purchased from Sigma (St. Louis, MO, USA). An Ultra-pure Water System (SG Ultra Clear system, Wasseraufbereitung und Regenerierstation GmbH, Germany) was used to produce ultra pure water with specific conductivity down to 0.055 µS/cm for the analysis of HPLC. Mixed stock solutions of daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein were prepared at concentrations of 20 µg/mL in methanol. Then, 0.5, 1.00, 2.00, 4.00, 8.00 and 10.00 µg/mL of the mixed standard solutions were prepared to yield a series of working solutions for the calibration curves. Mixed stock solutions were stored at 4 °C. Working solutions were prepared fresh daily by diluting mixed stock solutions with 85% solvent A and 15% solvent B mobile phase. A portion of the solution was then filtered through a 0.45 µm micro-filter prior to analysis.

Apparatus :

Prior to each analytical determination the *Radix scutellariae* was powdered with a high speed universal crusher machine (FW80, Beijing everlasting light instrument plant, Beijing, China). Rotary evaporator (RE-52AA, Shanghai Yarong Biochemical Co. Ltd., Shanghai, China) was used in experiment in order to remove the ethanol solvent. The HPLC system incorporated a Finnigan Surveyor Pump Plus (Thermo Finnigan, MA, USA), a Diode Array UV Detection (DAD) system (Thermo Finnigan, MA, USA) and a six-way rotary valve for sample introduction with a 20 µL sample loop. The column for analysis was an Akasil C18 column (4.6 × 150 mm I.D.; 5 µm pore size; Agela Technologies Co. Ltd., Shanghai, China), preceded by a C18 guard column (4.6 × 12.5 mm I.D.; 5 µm pore size; Agela Technologies Co. Ltd., Shanghai, China).

Chromatographic conditions :

In the HPLC analysis, the mobile phases consisted of solvents A and B. Solvent A was 99.8% ultra-pure water and 0.2% glacial acetic acid. Solvent B was acetonitrile. The mobile phase was pumped at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. A gradient program was used to achieve the best separation. The gradient conditions were as follows : from 0 to 5 min, holding 15% B; from 5 to 15 min, ramp to 35% B; from 15 to 40 min, ramp to 15% B. The total analysis time was 40 min. The sample injection volume was 20 µL. The temperature of the column was set at 25 °C. UV absorption of daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein was detected using a DAD measuring the maximum ab-

sorbance spectra at 254 nm, 263 nm, 282 nm and 288 nm, respectively.

Preparation of real samples :

For *Radix scutellariae* analysis, about 3.00 g of the sample was cut into small pieces by an operating scissors and homogenized with a high speed universal crusher machine. Then, 0.01 g powder of sample was transferred to a 25 mL beaker. In order to extract the isoflavonoids of *Radix scutellariae*, 15 mL 70% methanol was added into the beaker and the beaker was treated with ultrasonic bath for 20 min. After ultrasound the methanol solution was removed by rotary evaporator at 65 °C for 30 min. The residue was transferred into a volumetric flask and made up to 10 mL with methanol. Blank solutions were prepared in the same way as the samples. All solvents were filtered through a 0.45 µm micro-filter prior to injection, the samples were analyzed immediately after the pre-treatment. Six injections were performed for each sample.

Conclusions :

In the present study, we described a simple, reliable and sensitive method that allowed the determination of daidzin, daidzein, genistin and genistein concentrations in *Radix scutellariae*. This procedure, suitable for routine analyses, consists of direct injection, a simple sample pre-treatment, followed by an HPLC quantification step. The method was characterized by good precision, linearity and accuracy. The optimized procedure was applied to a wide medicinal herbs range to provide a general knowledge regarding the content of these isoflavones.

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